

Analysis of the Application of Problem Based Learning to Student's Critical Thinking Skills Material: Data Transmission Error Detection

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Abstract:

The purpose of Indonesian National Education is to develop the ability and shape the character of the nation based on Pancasila, by implementing an independent curriculum and forming the profile of Pancasila students who believe & fear God Almighty, have global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical and creative reasoning. Indonesian education is presented with various innovative learning models to attract and develop the abilities of 21st century learners. The research conducted aims to analyze the results of the application of the Problem Based Learning learning model on the critical thinking skills of class XI F4 students at SMA N 3 Surakarta as many as 36 students. Based on the results of research conducted using qualitative methods based on questionnaire assessments and student learning outcomes, it was found that the critical thinking skills of students in class XI F4 had a very good category, namely 61% on the results of the questionnaire and 67% on the test of student learning outcomes. Indicators of critical thinking skills of students in class XI F4 get 86% achievement on Advances clarification indicators and inference indicators. Based on the results of the research conducted, it is found that the problem-based learning model is effectively used to build students' critical thinking skills on error detection material in data transmission in class XI F4 SMA N 3 Surakarta.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking, Problem Based Learning*

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Introduction

Education in Indonesia is currently experiencing many changes compared to education before the 21st century. Based on the objectives of Indonesian national education as stated in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System: "National education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the nation's life, aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who are faithful and devoted to God Almighty, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens". To achieve these goals, one of the steps taken to provide progress in Indonesian education is to implement the Merdeka Curriculum.

The hope in implementing an independent curriculum in education in Indonesia is to form a national personality based on Pancasila, which has the character of the Pancasila Student Profile. The 6 characters included in the character of the Pancasila student profile are Believing & fearing God Almighty, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical and creative reasoning. To achieve the above goals, educators have an innovative learning model that is applied. Some of the innovative learning models applied include: Problem Based Learning, Project Based Learning, Discovery Learning, Cooperative Learning, Collaborative Learning, Contextual Learning, etc.

Critical thinking ability according to Norris and Ennis (1989), critical thinking is reasonable and reflective thinking which is aimed at making decisions about what is done or believed. The critical thinking ability of students is the skills of students in observing, asking questions, conducting experiments, interpreting experimental data, analyzing, making conclusions, and presentations expressed as very poor, poor, moderate, good, and very good (Suriasa 2018).

SMA N 3 Surakarta has implemented the Merdeka curriculum, but still has obstacles in developing students' analytical skills and students have not had many meaningful learning experiences, so the application of a problem-based learning model is important. One of the educators' methods to improve students' critical thinking skills is to use a problem-based learning model. Problem Based Learning According to Arends (2008), Problem Based Learning (PBL) is a learning model that presents a variety of authentic and meaningful problematic situations to learners, which can serve as a springboard for investigation and inquiry. PBL helps learners to develop critical thinking skills and problem-solving skills.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of the application of learning with a problem-based learning model on the critical thinking skills of students on the material of error detection in data transmission in high school informatics.

Related Work

Yelland, Cope, & Kalantzis (2008) in Etherington (2011:37) state Problem-based learning is a student-centered method of teaching that involves learning through solving unclear but genuine problems. It is a constructivist, student-focused approach that promotes reflection, skills in communication and collaboration, and it requires reflection from multiple perspectives. (Problem-based learning is a student-centered teaching method that involves learning through solving unclear but genuine problems. It is a constructivist, student-focused approach that promotes reflection, skills in communication and collaboration, and it requires reflection from multiple perspectives).

According to Arends (1997), "Problem-based teaching is a learning approach in which students work on authentic problems with a view to constructing their own knowledge, developing inquiry and higher-level thinking skills, developing independence and self-confidence" (Trianto, 2011:5).

Lin and Lee (2013) stated that critical thinking is a high-level thinking skills course. Skills, attitudes and knowledge elements and by questioning, introspection, liberation, reconstruction process can help learners get the ability to solve the problem, a reasonable judgment action based on a reasonable life. (Critical thinking is a high-level thinking skills program. Skills, attitudes, and elements of knowledge and by questioning, introspection, liberation, and reconstruction process can help learners get the ability to solve the problem, a reasonable judgment action based on a reasonable life). Masek and Yamin (2011: 217) state, Critical thinking is in the family of higher order thinking skills, along with creative thinking, problem solving, and decision making (Facione, 1990). (Critical thinking is included in higher order thinking skills, along with creative thinking, problem solving, and decision making).

According to Trianto (2010) argues that, "Thinking is the ability to analyze, criticize, and reach conclusions based on inference or careful consideration" (p.95). Critical thinking according to Glaser in Fisher (2009) is:

- 1) An attitude of being willing to think deeply about problems and things that are within one's range of experience;
- 2) Knowledge of logical methods of examination and reasoning; and
- 3) A kind of skill to apply these methods.

Relevant Research

In research conducted by Husnidar (2021) in the article "Application of Problem Based Learning Model to Improve Students' Mathematics Learning Outcomes" obtained results: the application of Problem Based Learning (PBL) is effectively used on scale material, this is shown in cycle 1 the percentage of learning completeness is 54% with an average score of 75.20, and in cycle 2 it increases to 95% with an average score of 82.11.

In research conducted by Desy Triana Dewi (2020) in the article "Application of Problem Based Learning to Improve Students' Critical Thinking Ability", the results showed that the critical thinking ability of students increased from cycle 1 by 50% to 87.5% in cycle 2, teacher activities showed an increase from cycle 1 of 74.76% to 91.9% in cycle 2, student activities increased from 78.19% in cycle 1 to 84.57% in cycle 2, and student responses were 89.06%. The conclusion from these results is that the application of the Problem Based Learning model can improve students' critical thinking skills.

In research conducted by Tiok Setiawan (2022) in the article "Analysis of the Application of Project Based Learning and Problem Based Learning Models to Elementary School Learners" obtained results: Both PjBL and PBL learning models can increase the activeness of students in learning activities, but when compared between the two models, the

PjBL model is found to be more active in the process of learning activities and good from the cognitive learning outcomes of students.

The difference between this research and previous research is that the subject of this research is students of class XI F4 SMA N 3 Surakarta with the object of applying the Problem Based Learning (PBL) learning model to improve critical thinking skills on error detection material in data transmission.

Research Method

The research was conducted at SMA N 3 Surakarta on 36 students in class XI F4 using qualitative research methods. Creswell in the book *Research Design*, states: "Qualitative research is a method for exploring and understanding the meaning that a number of individuals or groups of people ascribe to social or humanitarian problems. The qualitative research process involves important efforts, such as asking questions and procedures, collecting specific data from participants, analyzing data inductively from specific themes to general themes, and interpreting the meaning of the data. The final report for this research has a flexible structure or outline. Anyone involved in this form of research should adopt a research perspective that is inductive in style, focuses on individual meaning, and interprets the complexity of a problem". This research was conducted in class XI F4 with 8 students and 28 students, during PPL I which was held on February 29 - April 23, 2024.

Data collection techniques are in the form of filling out questionnaires and student learning outcomes, namely evaluation questions. The data analysis technique used is descriptive qualitative, namely in the form of data collection, reduction, presentation and conclusion drawing. The researcher is the main instrument in this research. The questionnaire given to students is the result of reflection on the application of the Problem Based Learning learning model related to critical thinking skills obtained after the learning process activities. Evaluation questions given in the form of 5 questions that include indicators of assessing the critical thinking skills of students which include: Simple explanation, basic support, reasoning, providing further explanation, and organizing strategies and tactics.

The procedures used in this research are the planning stage, the implementation stage, the observation stage and the reflection stage. In the planning stage carried out before the research was the preparation of teaching modules with error detection material in data transmission which was given 3 times a meeting with the Problem-based learning model. In the implementation stage, the activities carried out consisted of 3 preliminary activities, core activities, and closing activities. In these learning activities include: Orientation to the problem, learning organization, group investigation, presentation of problem solving results, analysis and evaluation of solutions. In the observation stage, the process of collecting data on learning outcomes was carried out at the 3rd meeting. The reflection process is carried out after each learning process.

The rubric for assessing questionnaires and student learning outcomes using the Problem Based Learning learning model is as follows:

Table 1. Questionnaire scoring rubric

Score	Description
1	Never
2	Sometimes
3	Often
4	Always

Table 2: Rating scale for critical thinking skills level

Rate	Meaning
85-100	Very Good
75-84	Good
60-74	Simply
<60	Less

No Soal	Indikator Penilaian	Skor Tes kemampuan berpikir kritis	
		Rubrik Penilaian	Skor
1	Penjelasan Sederhana	Jawaban Tidak memahami soal	1
		Menganalisis asumsi dengan mengidentifikasi relevansi permasalahan namun belum benar	2
		Menganalisis asumsi dengan mengidentifikasi relevansi permasalahan dengan benar	3
		Menganalisis asumsi dengan mengidentifikasi relevansi permasalahan dengan benar dan lengkap	4
2	Dukungan dasar	Jawaban Tidak memahami soal	1
		Memberikan dukungan dasar dengan benar	2
		Memberikan dukungan dasar dengan benar dan kurang lengkap	3
		Memberikan dukungan dasar dengan benar dan lengkap	4
3	Penalaran	Tidak ada solusi dari permasalahan	1
		Menuliskan alternatif atau solusi namun belum benar	2
		Menuliskan alternatif atau solusi dari permasalahan dalam soal dengan benar	3
		Menuliskan alternatif atau solusi dari permasalahan dalam soal dengan benar dan lengkap	4
4	Memberikan penjelasan lebih lanjut	Tidak memberikan identifikasi asumsi	1
		Mengidentifikasi asumsi namun belum benar	2
		Mengidentifikasi asumsi dengan benar	3
		Mengidentifikasi asumsi dengan benar dan lengkap	4
5	Mengatur strategi dan taktik	Tidak menuliskan kesimpulan	1
		Menuliskan kesimpulan namun belum benar	2
		Menuliskan kesimpulan dengan benar	3
		Menuliskan kesimpulan dengan benar dan lengkap	4

Figure 1. Critical thinking skills scale assessment rubric based on answers to learning outcomes of evaluation questions

Total Critical Thinking Ability Score = Total Score x 5

The value of students' critical thinking ability is measured based on the total summation of the score answers obtained multiplied by 5. The maximum total score is 100 from 5 questions.

Result and Discussion

The learning process uses a problem-based learning model by implementing several syntaxes, namely:

1. Orienting students to the problem
2. Organizing students to learn
3. Guiding individual and group investigations
4. Developing and presenting work
5. Analyzing and evaluating the problem-solving process

The application of these activities in learning is expected to build the development of students in terms of critical thinking which includes several aspects, namely: Simple explanation, basic support, reasoning, providing further explanation and organizing strategies and tactics.

Learning activities are divided into 3 activities, namely: Preliminary activities which contain the opening of the teaching and learning process by the teacher accompanied by prayer and providing information on learning objectives as well as providing apperception and motivation to build students' enthusiasm for learning in learning. The core activities are filled with applying the syntax of the problem-based learning model which is previously carried out assessment diagnostic to find out the initial knowledge data of students regarding error detection material in data transmission. In the core activities, formative assessment is also carried out to determine the learning outcomes of students to measure the level of critical thinking skills of students. Then continued in the 3rd activity, namely the closing activity which contains conclusions from students that are reinforced by the teacher and giving feedback to students on the learning that has been done by the educator. Followed by providing information about the material that will be given at the next meeting.

Result

From the results of research that has been conducted in class XI F4 SMA N 3 Surakarta on 36 students, the following results were obtained

Figure 2. Questionnaire results of the application of problem-based learning model in class XI F4

The critical thinking ability of students in class XI F4 based on research has a very good average of more than half of the class, namely 61%, and good results reach 39%. While the categories are sufficient and less than 0%. This is obtained based on the results of a questionnaire distributed to students as many as 12 statements with the categories Always, Often, Sometimes and Never.

The following is the data on the results of the questionnaire per statement:

Figure 3. 12 Questionnaire Result Data

To validate students' critical thinking skills according to their claims, validation is carried out by giving evaluation questions to measure students' critical thinking skills based on 5 indicators of learning outcomes. The following are

the learning outcomes of students using the Problem Based Learning model on error detection material in data transmission.

Figure 4. Level of critical thinking skills of students based on learning outcomes

Based on the results of validation of students' critical thinking skills using evaluation questions, it was found that 67% of students in class XI F4 had very good critical thinking skills, 22% of students had good critical thinking skills, 11% of students had sufficient critical thinking skills. From the results of this validation, the ability to think critically very well has increased by 6% compared to the claims of students through questionnaires, while the good category has dropped to 22% and the remaining 11% are in the moderate category.

Figure 5. Percentage of students' critical thinking skills per indicator

Based on the data above, more than 70% of students in class XI F4 have very good critical thinking skills in each of the indicators. The indicators with the highest achievement are Advances Clarification and inference which reached 86%, while the indicators with the lowest achievement were elementary clarification and basic support which reached 72%. Elementary clarification is related to the ability to focus questions, analyze questions and ask, and answer questions about an explanation or statement. Learners tend to do little questioning activity when other groups present their work. Basic support relates to the ability to consider whether a source is reliable or not and to observe and consider an observation report. Learners still lack literacy and are not accustomed to including references and sources of information obtained.

Discussion

Based on the results of the analysis conducted, it was found that the relationship between the syntax of the problem-based learning model and aspects of critical thinking skills:

1. Orienting students to the problem builds students' abilities in simple explanations
2. Organizing students to learn to build basic support skills
3. Guiding individual and group investigations builds the ability to provide further explanations
4. Developing and presenting work results builds the ability to organize strategies and tactics
5. Analyzing and evaluating the problem-solving process builds reasoning skills

Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that:

1. The Problem Based Learning learning model is effectively used on the material of error detection in data transmission of phase F informatics subjects in class XI F4 at SMA N 3 Surakarta.
2. Critical thinking skills of students in class XI F4 using the questionnaire method obtained very good results in 61% of students.
3. The critical thinking ability of students in class XI F4 using the evaluation of learning outcomes obtained very good results in 67% of students.
4. Students' critical thinking skills based on 5 indicators obtained more than 70% achievement per indicator.

To increase the critical thinking skills of students can then use other innovative learning models. Providing active learner activities will affect the critical thinking skills of students. As an educator, researchers must improve their ability to understand the characteristics of students and the ability of 21st century technology to attract students' interest in learning, so that the use of learning models with various methods can achieve the desired learning objectives.

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